

emphasizing ergonomic constraints based on operator stature. A skeletal tracking system makes it possible to compute an ergonomic trajectory that all agents can execute [9].

Central Node. Serving as the execution hub, the Central Node oversees task primitives and supervises the workcell's state using various sensors. Central Node also handle human requests [10] and communicates with the Task and Motion planner to execute the requited action.

II. EXPERIMENTS

The proposed task planner capable of adapting to human behavior in a dynamic environment was tested on a real industrial use case. To evaluate its performances, we exploited this system on the process of collaborative draping carbon fiber plies. Our evaluation involved: (i) the analysis of the computational time taken to create an appropriate plan, including the replanning phase triggered by the user interactions, (ii) the performance of the Human Action Recognition system, (iii) a qualitative analysis of the Task Planner's performance in the real industrial workcell at DLR's facility (Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Augsburg, Germany).

Draping is a complex industrial operation that requires an advanced skilled user who is not only responsible for draping onto the mould but also for a series of activities such as inspecting the part, annotating by text and/or photos certain areas of the ply if they have slight defects, and checking that the orientation of the fibres is correct. In this application, the transport of a ply could be executed by the operator alone or the robot alone, or it could be a collaborative transport where human and robot are both involved [11], [12]. Thus, coordinating the actions of the human-agent and the robotic agent is crucial. As mentioned above, once the plan is generated, this is not static. The operator can use a gesture to stop the robot's action or trigger an action not in the original plan. The user can also overwrite the plan and notify the central node that the current action has been completed and instructed to move on to the next action. An example of this situation is when the operator has finished draping the ply and wants to notify the central node so that it can perform the next action. This is a simple and intuitive way for the user to interact with the robots and provide his/her experience into the system. Analyzing the process and the activities to be done, we identified a set of gestures of interest based on the possible human-robot interactions which can arise during the process. In particular, a set of 6 human actions has been considered: Detection, Inspection, Transport, Draping, Drape Next and Take Picture. A configuration file is used to represent the precedence constraints on the different actions and defines the order in which the plies are draped.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we examine the limitations of the traditional TAMP approaches in HRC scenarios. Specifically, these conventional methods could be improved to manage the dynamism and uncertainty introduced by users into an industrial HRC process. We identify and discuss the challenges the TAMP

framework should address, using the carbon fibre draping process as a real-world example. Finally, we describe the ongoing TAMP method in developed to try to address these industrial challenges.

More details on the evaluation of the system and on the achieved performances can be found in our previous works. See for the evaluation of the Task Planner [8] and for the collision-free volume estimation deformation algorithm [12].

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